

A Preliminary Study on Gyroscope-Based Gait Characteristics Between Left-Affected Side and Right-Affected Side Stroke Patients

Thanita Sanghan¹, Nusreena Hohsoh¹, Desmond Y.R. Chong², Surapong Chatpun¹

¹Department of Biomedical Sciences and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Medicine, Prince of Songkla University, Songkhla, Thailand.

²Engineering Cluster, Singapore Institute of Technology, Singapore.

Abstract:

Background: A gyroscope has been introduced for a motion detection, especially fall detection and gait analysis. Stroke patients usually have abnormal patterns during walking compared to healthy subjects. There is an interesting point to distinguish the similarity and non-similarity of gait characteristics between left-affected side and right-affected side stroke patients.

Objective: To preliminarily test the hypothesis that left-affected side stroke patients have similar gait characteristics as right-affected side stroke patients.

Methods: Stroke patients and healthy subjects were recruited. Two inertial measurement units were attached to a participant's lateral shanks on both sides to assess shank angular velocity during walking. All participants performed two 10-metre walk tests at their preferred speed, repeated three times. The temporal and 3-plane kinematic parameters were computed. For this preliminary study, the data from 10 stroke patients and 5 healthy subjects were analyzed.

Results: The stride time of the stroke patients was longer than that of the healthy subjects, whether they were affected on the left side or the right side. The stroke patients spent shorter stance and longer swing periods on the affected side while stance and swing time were similar on both sides in healthy subjects. The root mean square (RMS) values of angular velocity of the affected and non-affected sides were lower than those of the healthy subjects in three-plane motion. In the sagittal plane, the mean differences of angular velocity of the healthy subjects were 67% and 51% in the stance phase and 66% and 53% in the swing phase of the left-affected and right-affected sides, respectively.

Conclusion: There was a similar tendency in gyroscope-based gait characteristics of left-affected side and right-affected side stroke patients when compared with healthy subjects.

Keywords: gyroscope, stroke, abnormal gait, affected side, kinematic parameters

